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In the context of global climate change and increasing environmental risks, green finance is becoming a key tool for sustainable development of the global economy. In this context, international standards that ensure transparency, comparability, and trust in financial instruments supporting environmentally oriented projects are particularly important. This article examines the key international green finance standards, including Green Bonds, the ICMA Green Bond Principles, and the EU Taxonomy. It analyzes their essence, objectives, structure, and role in developing a unified approach to classifying "green" economic activities. Particular attention is paid to the importance of these standards for the development of sustainable financial markets, minimizing the risks of "greenwashing," and attracting private capital to environmental projects.

Keywords: green finance, green bonds, Green Bonds, ICMA, Green Bond Principles, EU Taxonomy, sustainable development, ESG, climate investments, greenwashing.

1. Introduction.

The modern global economy is developing in the face of growing environmental and climate challenges, including global warming, rising greenhouse gas emissions, and the degradation of natural ecosystems. In response to these challenges, the concept of sustainable development is actively being developed at the international level, integrating environmental, social, and economic factors into financial and investment decision-making¹. The key instrument for implementing this concept is the green finance system, aimed at mobilizing financial resources to support projects that contribute to the mitigation of climate change and adaptation to it². In recent years, the green financial instruments market has demonstrated steady growth, with green bonds occupying a special place in its structure, widely used by public and private issuers³. However, the rapid development of the green bond market has revealed the problem of the lack of uniform criteria for classifying projects as environmentally sustainable, which increases the risk of unfair use of funds and the spread of greenwashing practices.⁴In this regard, the role of international standards, ensuring transparency, comparability, and reliability of information for investors and regulators, is increasing.

Of key importance among such standards are the ICMA Green Bond Principles, which are a voluntary market-based regulatory mechanism, and the European Union Taxonomy, which is based on a normatively established system for classifying environmentally sustainable economic activities⁵. Their use helps build trust in the green finance market and increases its investment attractiveness. The purpose of this article is to analyze international green finance standards and assess their role in the development of sustainable financial markets. This objective involves examining international experience, conducting a comparative analysis

of key standards, and drawing conclusions that have practical implications for the development of national green finance systems.

2. Methodological aspects of the research.

The methodological basis of the research was a combination of general scientific and specialized methods for analyzing economic processes in the field of sustainable finance. The work employed methods of analysis and synthesis, induction and deduction, and a systems approach, allowing for the examination of green finance as an element of the global financial architecture⁶. A comparative method was used to compare the ICMA Green Bond Principles and the European Union Taxonomy to identify their functional and institutional differences. Economic and statistical methods were applied to analyze the dynamics of the global green bond market and the structure of financed projects.

An institutional approach allowed us to assess the role of international organizations and regulators in shaping green finance standards and mitigating the risks of greenwashing. The study's information base included official reports from international financial institutions, EU regulations, and scientific publications by international researchers.

3. International experience of the research.

The research shows that green finance has been most developed in the European Union, where a comprehensive regulatory framework for sustainable finance has been established. The central element of this system is the EU Taxonomy, which establishes uniform criteria for the environmental sustainability of economic activity⁷.

In the US and Asia-Pacific, green finance is being developed primarily through voluntary standards, in particular the ICMA Green Bond Principles, which are widely adopted by issuers and institutional investors⁸.

¹Sachs JD The Age of Sustainable Development. New York: Columbia University Press, 2015.

²OECD. Developing Sustainable Finance Definitions and Taxonomies, Paris, 2021.

³Climate Bonds Initiative. Global Green Bond Market Summary, London, 2023.

⁴World Bank. Green Bond Impact Report, Washington, DC, 2023.

⁵European Commission. EU Taxonomy for Sustainable Activities, Brussels, 2022.

⁶OECD. Developing Sustainable Finance Definitions and Taxonomies, Paris, 2021.

⁷European Commission. EU Taxonomy for Sustainable Activities, Brussels, 2022.

⁸International Capital Market Association (ICMA). Green Bond Principles, London, 2023.

China has developed a national taxonomy of green projects focused on domestic sustainable development priorities, and is working to align it with international standards. International financial institutions, including the World Bank and regional development banks, are actively using green bonds to finance climate and infrastructure projects, promoting the dissemination of best practices in green finance in developing countries.

It's worth noting that in 2023, one of China's largest commercial banks, The Industrial and Commercial Bank of China (ICBC), achieved significant results in green financing in the areas of wind energy, clean transportation, solar energy, energy-saving, and environmental projects. These projects not only provide financial support for green transformations in the country but also effectively contribute to environmental conservation. China Construction Bank launched a Low Carbon Loan product designed to provide financial support for energy conservation and emission reduction. The bank has supported a number of green projects for industrial upgrading through the construction of energy-efficient buildings and green industrial parks. Bank of China has diversified its green financial products and launched funds that specialize in investing in green development projects. Bank of China is actively involved in the carbon finance market to help enterprises optimize carbon management. Below are some key trends in the development of green banking. Integration of policy support and market mechanisms. The Chinese government is actively promoting policies related to green finance, creating a solid foundation for green banking. In the future, as policies are further refined, market mechanisms for green banking will gradually expand. The Chinese government has developed important policy documents, such as the "Catalogue of Green Bond-Supported Projects" and the "Green Finance Evaluation Program", which provide standards and support for the implementation of green financial products. For example, in 2023, the Ministry of Finance and the People's Bank of China (PBOC) jointly released the Green Finance Development Plan (2023–2027), which proposes strengthening financial support for green projects and supporting the development of green loans, green bonds, and other financial instruments. Furthermore, the government provides dedicated green finance funds through policy banks and commercial banks to facilitate investment in green projects⁹.

Green Finance Support Mechanisms in Developed Countries United Kingdom. The UK government has high ambitions to create a low-carbon, energy-efficient and environmentally sustainable economy. Active efforts to transition to a green economy in the United Kingdom began with the adoption of the Climate

Change Act 2008, which aims to reduce carbon dioxide emissions by 80% by 2050 compared to the 1990 baseline. However, not only national environmental goals were defined, but also European Union (hereinafter referred to as the EU) goals: achieving 15% of all energy production from renewable sources (EU Renewable Energy Directive); recycling 50% of household waste by 2020 and reducing the landfill of biodegradable municipal waste by 35% by 2020 compared to 1995 (EU Waste Framework Directive), etc.¹⁰. But the transition to a green economy in the UK requires significant investment. For example, at least £100 billion is needed in energy (renewable energy, carbon capture and storage, electricity transmission, etc.); approximately £10 billion by 2020 for renewable heat; and £14 to £21 billion for home energy efficiency. The Green Investment Bank (GIB) Commission has identified a number of barriers hindering investment in green projects in the UK¹¹. An independent and non-partisan advisory group convened by the UK Chancellor of the Exchequer to support and attract private sector investment in a low-carbon economy as investment market capacity limits and balance sheet constraints; political and regulatory risks; lack of investor confidence given technology risks, a lack of transparency in government policy, and high capital requirements for commercialization; difficulty attracting institutional investors to large numbers of small, low-carbon projects. The Green Investment Bank (GIB), which began operations in October 2012, was established by the UK government to address these barriers and attract investment in green projects. The main objectives of this institution are to eliminate market failures and stimulate private sector investment in green infrastructure projects. The Bank uses the following main instruments: loans and equity investments, investment fund financing, and guarantees¹². To date, the Green Investment Bank has committed £2.3 billion to 58 projects across a range of sectors, mobilizing £7.8 billion of private capital, with £3 of additional private capital coming in for every £1 invested by the government¹³. Another instrument of government support for green project financing is the British Business Bank, whose primary goal is to increase financing for small and medium-sized businesses. This bank does not provide financial resources directly, but rather operates through partners. For example, the VC Catalyst Fund program, which supports venture capital funds, is a key player in this area.

South Korea Global warming, high dependence on fossil fuels and the economic crisis have served as pre-conditions for the transition to a green economy.

The transition to a green economy began in earnest with the announcement of the national "low-carbon

⁹<https://www.climatepolicyinitiative.org/publication/green-banking-in-china-emerging-trends/>

¹⁰HM Government. Update on the design of the Green Investment Bank. 2011. URL: https://www.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/31825/11-917-update-design-green-investment-bank.pdf

¹¹Green Investment Bank Commission. Unlocking investment to deliver Britain's low carbon future // Report. London: Green Investment Bank Commission. 2010. URL:

https://www.e3g.org/docs/Unlocking_investment_to_deliver_Britains_low_carbon_future_-_Green_Investment_Bank_Commission_Report_June_2010.pdf

¹²UK Green Investment Bank. Annual Report 2014. Edinburgh. 2014. URL: <http://www.greeninvestmentbank.com/media/25360/ar14-web-version-v2-final.pdf>

¹³Department for Business, Innovation & Skills. Future of UK Green Investment Bank plc // Policy paper BIS/15/630. 2015. 24 p. URL: https://www.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/477493/BIS-15-630-future-of-the-ukgreen-investment-bank.pdf

green growth” strategy by President Lee Myung-Bak in November 2008. To implement this strategy, a five-year green growth plan (2009–2013) was adopted in July 2009. According to the plan, US\$83.6 billion, which is 2% of the gross domestic product, is to be spent¹⁴. The Korean government is focusing primarily

on large-scale construction projects within the framework of the “Green New Deal” (restoring four major rivers, building 1 million green homes by 2020, high-speed rail, etc.). The first five-year plan also discusses a strategy to attract private investment in this area and includes the following steps¹⁵:

Figure 1. South Korea's Five-Year Green Growth Plan¹⁶

In the course of implementing this strategy, Korean business groups invested 15.1 trillion won (approximately \$13.6 billion) in the green sector, up from 2.4 trillion (\$2.2 billion) in 2008, 5.4 trillion (\$4.9 billion) in 2009, and 7.3 trillion (\$6.6 billion) in 2010. These figures represent a 74.5% increase in annual investment between 2008 and 2010. According to the OECD report (OECD Economic Surveys: Korea 2012), the main factor hindering private investment in green business and innovation is the availability of financing, especially at the start-up stage. Traditional mechanisms cannot be used due to risks, such as information asymmetry. Therefore, to improve access to finance, the government passed the Framework Act on Low Carbon, Green Growth, which establishes and requires the government to develop financial instruments to provide direct financial support to green businesses and encourage private investment in green infrastructure projects¹⁷. Green financing in South Korea is provided through bank loans and loan guarantees. It can also be implemented through the venture capital market. Green

bank loans are provided through conventional commercial banks and public financial institutions. In Korea, 75% of all green loans are provided by publicly funded banks. There are three types of green lending: direct lending, refinancing, and green deposit schemes¹⁸. Direct lending is carried out through government-funded banks directly to “green” companies. The scheme, where the government directs funds to commercial banks through the Korea Finance Corporation (KoFC) and then to “green” companies, is called on-lending. In the “green” deposit scheme, the government does not participate directly, but offers tax breaks to those who invest in “green” projects at a low interest rate. Credit guarantees are provided in South Korea by two main financial institutions: the Korea Credit Guarantee Fund (KODIT) and the Korea Technology Finance Corp. (KIBO). Also of special note is the Export-Import Bank of Korea (KEXIM), which issued “green” bonds in the amount of US\$500 million for a five-year term with a coupon income of 1.75%. It uses various types of lending (export and import loans, guarantees, etc.)¹⁹. But other financial institutions in Korea are also investing

¹⁴UNEP. Overview of the Republic of Korea's National Strategy for Green Growth. 2010. URL: http://www.unep.org/PDF/PressReleases/201004_unep_national_strategy.pdf

¹⁵Zelenovskaya E. Green growth policy in Korea: a case study. International Center for Climate Governance. URL: http://www.iccgov.org/wp-content/uploads/2015/05/08_reflection_june_2012.pdf

¹⁶Prepared by the author.

¹⁷OECD. OECD Economic Surveys: Korea 2012. 2012. 146 p. URL: <https://books.google.ru/books?id=prlEtEgVnjkc/>

¹⁸Kim Hyoung-tae. System Architecture for Effective Green Finance in Korea // Korea's Economy. 2011. T. 27. Pp. 18–24. URL: http://www.keia.org/sites/default/files/publications/30848_kimht_sp.pdf

¹⁹Korea Eximbank. GreenBond // KOREA EXIMBANK GREEN BOND NEWSLETTER. 2015. URL: http://ehf.koreaexim.go.kr/File.download?file=/attach_file/conts/kr/bank/Green%20Bond%20Investor%20Letter.pdf

in the green sector. For example, Kookmin Bank (the country's largest lender) established a 330 billion won Renewable Energy Direct Investment Fund with the government and allocated 750 billion won for investments in low-carbon, green growth industries²⁰. To reduce information risk, South Korea has a green certification system, which is outlined in the Framework Act on Low Carbon, Green Growth. It consists of two components such as the Green Certification Committee (GCC) and the Korea Institute of Advancement of Technology (KIAT). The GCC determines which technologies and projects qualify for green certification

based on the assessment of the Korea Institute of Advancement of Technology (KIAT)²¹.

Germany was one of the first countries to implement "green" policies, having put forward its first federal environmental program in 1971²². In 1973, the first oil crisis led to a sharp increase in the price of oil, which led to the adoption of the Energy Conservation Act (EnEG) in 1976. This act encouraged investments in environmental protection through interest rate subsidies²³. In July 2007, following the G8 meeting, the German government set targets no less ambitious than those of the UK for 2020, compared with 1990²⁴.

a 40% reduction in greenhouse gas emissions;

- increasing the share of renewable energy sources to at least 30%;

increasing the share of renewable thermal energy sources to 14%; – doubling energy efficiency;

- doubling the capacity of combined heat and power (CHP) plants with a 25% increase in electricity generation volumes.

Figure 2. Green policy priorities in Germany²⁵

Since 2007, the German government has issued a number of measures aimed at achieving these goals, which include various environmental regulations and requirements (e.g., from January 1, 2009, owners of new homes must provide heating and cooling from renewable energy sources; setting limits on greenhouse gas emissions from vehicles; tax breaks for the implementation of energy management systems in enterprises from 2013, etc.)²⁶. State financial support for green projects in Germany is provided by the national investment bank Kreditanstalt für Wiederaufbau

(KfW), which was established in 1948 to implement the Marshall Plan. The bank is jointly owned by the German federal government (80%) and the states (20%)²⁷. KfW's main areas of environmental financing are renewable energy, energy efficiency, and low-carbon transport. In 2011, €22.8 billion was allocated for environmental financing, accounting for one-third of the bank's funding for incentive and development programs. The bank supports green projects through the following instruments²⁸.

²⁰Kim Jae-Kyoung. Korea Braces for Green Finance Era // The Korea Times. 2009. URL: http://www.koreatimes.co.kr/www/news/biz/2015/12/283_49962.html

²¹OECD Economic Surveys: Korea 2012. 2012. 146 p. URL: <https://books.google.ru/books?id=prlEtEgVnjc/>

²²Gill, Indermit S., Raiser, Martin (2013). Golden growth: restoring the lustre of the European economic model (Vol. 3): Country benchmarks. Washington DC, World Bank. 2013. URL: <http://documents.worldbank.org/curated/en/394981468251372492/pdf/681680PUB0v30G00Box379869B00PUBLIC0.pdf>

²³Schröder M. et al. The KfW experience in the reduction of energy use in and CO2 emissions from buildings: operation, impacts and lessons for the UK. UCL Energy Institute. 2011. 77 p. URL: <http://sticerd.lse.ac.uk/dps/case/cp/KfWFullReport.pdf>

²⁴Federal Ministry for the Environment, Nature Conservation and Nuclear Safety (BMUB). Green Recovery: The Way out of the Economic Crisis. Berlin: BMU. 2009. URL:

https://www.germany.info/contentblob/2618342/Daten/676538/BMU_GreenRecovery_DD.pdf

²⁵Prepared by author.

²⁶Federal Ministry for the Environment, Nature Conservation, Building and Nuclear Safety (BMUB). Climate Protection in Figures. Facts, Trends and Incentives for German Climate Policy. 2014. URL: http://www.phnom-penh.diplo.de/contentblob/4549730/Daten/4583205/Climate_Protection.pdf.

²⁷Christopher J. Wigley. Chapter 15. Revitalizing the Green Investment Bank // The Green Book: New Directions for Liberals in Government / ed. D. Brack. London: Biteback Publishing. 2013. 384 p. URL: <https://books.google.ru/books?id=JwKuAwAAQBAJ/>

²⁸Hubert R., Cochran I. Public Finance Institutions & the Low-Carbon Transition Case Study: KfW Bankengruppe // CDC Climat Research. 2013. URL: http://www.i4ce.org/wp-core/wp-content/uploads/2015/10/14-09_kfw_case_study.pdf

Figure 3. Tools to support green projects in banks

The bank's investment activities are primarily carried out by providing preferential loans through lending to local financial institutions. For large-scale project financing, KfW provides direct lending at market rates, eliminating the market gap²⁹. KfW Bank is financed by private and public funds. However, the most important sources of funding for the bank are international capital and money markets. More than 90% of the bank's capital comes from capital markets, and in 2010, more than €76 billion was raised from international capital markets³⁰. One of the instruments for attracting financing for KfW's green projects are green bonds. The bank issued its first green bonds in 2014 for a total of €2.7 billion. One separate measure of state support for financing green projects in Germany is the Feed-in Tariff (FIT), which encourages investments in renewable energy sources. This program was first established in Germany by the *Stromeinspeisungsgesetz (StrEG)* (Electricity Feed-in Act) in 1990, and by the *Erneuerbare-Energien-Gesetz (EEG)* (Renewable Energy Act) in 2000. According to this program, it is necessary to connect producers of electricity from renewable sources and purchase this electricity. Financing of this program is carried out by distributing costs among all consumers, which guarantees low electricity prices³¹. In addition to the state-owned investment bank, there are a number of financial institutions in Germany that offer "ethical financial products" (environmentally and socially oriented) or "ethical banking" as GLS bank, TriodosBank, Umweltbank, EthikBank.

4. Analysis and results of the research.

The analysis shows that the ICMA Green Bond Principles and EU Taxonomy serve complementary

functions within the system of international green finance standards. The ICMA Principles focus on the financing process and disclosure, establishing requirements for the intended use of funds, revenue management, and issuer reporting. In contrast, EU Taxonomy is based on a classification approach and defines specific environmental objectives, including climate change mitigation and adaptation, as well as technical criteria for assessing project sustainability. This promotes the unification of approaches to assessing green investments and increases investor confidence. An analysis of international practice confirms that the use of taxonomy reduces information asymmetry in financial markets and improves the efficiency of capital allocation. However, developing economies still need to adapt international standards to their national conditions and institutional environments.

5. Conclusion.

The research concludes that international green finance standards are a key factor in the development of sustainable financial markets. The ICMA Green Bond Principles ensure the flexibility and scalability of green financial instruments, while the EU Taxonomy establishes uniform and clear criteria for environmental sustainability.

The comprehensive use of these standards helps reduce the risks of greenwashing, increase the transparency of financial flows, and attract long-term investment in environmental projects. International experience can be used to develop national green finance models and integrate ESG principles into public financial policies.

²⁹Hubert R., Cochran I. Public Finance Institutions & the Low-Carbon Transition Case Study: KfW Bankengruppe // CDC Climat Research. 2013. URL: http://www.i4ce.org/wp-core/wp-content/uploads/2015/10/14-09_kfw_case_study.pdf

³⁰Dolphin T., Nash D. Investing for the future: Why we need a British Investment Bank. Institute for Public Policy Research. 2010.

(http://www.ippr.org/files/images/media/files/publication/2012/09/investment-future-BIB_Sep2012_9635.pdf?noredirect=1)

³¹Mendonça M., Corre J. Success story: Feed-in tariffs support renewable energy in Germany. 2009. URL: http://www.e-parl.net/eparliament/pdf/080603_%20FIT%20toolkit.pdf

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12. <https://www.climatepolicyinitiative.org/publication/green-banking-in-china-emerging-trends/>
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